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FOREWORD

**Journal of Academic Staff Union of Polytechnics (ASUP)
Nekede Owerri Chapter
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Quality and scholarly research papers are invited from the academics and members of the public on any, but not necessarily limited to the underlisted sub-themes/areas. The ASUPNEK JOURNAL, the maiden edition of ASUPNEK JOURNAL, USA will publish the work and findings of scholars and experts on contemporary issues.

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- 2. It should be typed double – line spacing on A4 paper.
- 3. Only empirical papers would be published in the journal.
- 4. The article should be on Microsoft word windows XP 2007.

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PERCEIVED EFFECTS OF STAFF MOTIVATION ON TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF BUSINESS EDUCATION TEACHERS IN POLYTECHNICS, IMO STATE

Onwukwe Chukwuemeka Ozioma S.

Abstract

The study was carried out to determine the perceived effects of staff motivation on teaching performance of business education teachers in public-owned polytechnics in Imo State. Four research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The instruments for data collection were structured questionnaires designed by the researcher and face-validated by experienced educationists in Enugu State College of Education (Technical). A correlation coefficient reliability of 0.99 was established for the instrument. Population of the study is 195 teachers in one federal and state public-owned polytechnic, Imo State. Thereafter, a sample of 60 business education teachers was selected for the study. T- test was used to analyze the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings showed that four major areas of job security, enhanced welfare scheme, remunerations and in-service training will help to improve the motivation status on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State, if properly harnessed. One of the recommendations is that management of academic institutions should fast-track training and re-training of business education teachers to enable them actualize their educational goals and objectives.

Introduction

The school as an organization is set up with desired objectives, which can be accomplished through the combined efforts of the teaching staff on one hand, and invariably the school administration and the constituted authority on the other hand. Education system like other social systems depends largely on their caliber of personnel (teachers) that are found within the system for it to actualize its set objectives and goals, and for the personnel to perform optimally, they have to be motivated.

Motivation is eagerness and willingness to do something without needing to be told or forced to do it. Motivation is an inner drive to behave or act in a certain manner. These inner conditions such as wishes, desires and goals, activate to move in a particular direction in behavior. It is the reason behind why someone wants to do something and to work hard in order to do it, especially because he finds it interesting or exciting. Studies from Ralph Nader's *Leadership and Motivation*, Charles T. Schmidt's *Leader Behavior and Motivation* and Nakpođia E.D's *Leadership development skills: a Nigeria educational institutions review* have shown that motivation and good leadership management are central factors in the effective influencing of people at work. Motivation has been shown to have roots in psychological, behavioral, cognitive and social areas. Motivation may be rooted in a basic impulse to optimize well-being, pain and maximize pleasure. It can also originate from specific physical needs such as eating, sleeping or resting and sex, (Retrieved September 20, 2014 from <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Motivation>).

Motivation is a term derived from the latin word 'movere' which means to move. Thus, staff motivation is described as what energizes human behavior, what directs or channels such behavior and how the behavior is maintained and sustained. Staff motivation is the additional incentive given to teachers/workers in order to induce them to work harder. In many organizations and/or institutions like school, teachers/workers had been motivated among others with office and residential accommodation, vehicle loans, allowances, medical facilities, promotion, etc, (Oluchukwu, 2000).

According to Ejili and Anyanwu, (2006), teaching is a systematic, rational and organized process of transmitting knowledge, attitude and skills in accordance with professional principles. Teaching is said to be a complex task. It involves all those activities and processes through which people learn useful and worthwhile ideas and skills. It is a

veritable instrument of socialization and education. It is seen as the human efforts geared towards transferring values from one who is more knowledgeable to one who is less knowledgeable.

Business education refers to a special course of study or a branch of knowledge offered at the polytechnic level. Primary emphasis is placed on special methods of teaching business subjects, rather than on skill acquisition in the traditional skill subject areas of typewriting and shorthand. Such curriculum consisted of general education component, general business subjects component, secretarial component, marketing and distribution subjects, professional education component, accounting as well as industrial work experience. The mission of business education at the polytechnic level is to train the necessary manpower for industry, business, public and private business establishments. Business education opens various career opportunities to its graduates, namely: teaching in schools at various levels (depending on the level of degree and teaching qualification obtained), working in commerce, and the public sectors of the economy, undergoing advanced studies in business, taking up management positions in various organizations, and developing training programmes for industries and businesses.

The term Business Education was first given prominence in 1958 by the United States National Defence Act (NDEA), and the famous Conant Report in 1958. Both the Conant Report and the NDEA have advanced the cause of the American Education programme by endorsing the comprehensive high school curriculum. A business education teacher is a person who is knowledgeable in the six components of courses that make up a business education programme. In other words, a business education teacher is any person who plays the critical role in making business education viable and visible in the community, plays the role of agent of change in business education, delivers high quality business education programmes that are equal to any academic offering in the school system, is able to identify problems facing learning and teaching in business education subjects and ability to speculate solutions to these problems. Professional teacher of business education programme in many institutions, have been promoted and their jobs security have been given attention and implemented, making him or her to be constantly aware of the state of the art in business education, (Igboke, 2012).

This study is focused on how perceived effects of staff motivation affect in the teaching performance of business education teachers in the two public-owned polytechnics in Imo State. These polytechnics are Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri and Imo State Polytechnic Umuagwo, Ohaji. The Federal Polytechnic Nekede Owerri started in 1978 as the College of Technology, Owerri. It was established by the Imo State Government through Edict No.16 of April 1978. It took off at its temporary site at the premises of Government Technical College (GTC), Owerri along Egbu Road in the same year. In 1981, the institution moved to its present and permanent location at Nekede in Owerri. By the Imo State Government Edict No.6 of 1987, the name of the institution was changed to, "The Polytechnic Nekede Owerri." Six years after and precisely on 7th April 1993, the Federal Government had it renamed again to: "The Federal Polytechnic, Nekede, Owerri". The Imo State Polytechnic Umuagwo, Ohaji was established in the year 1978, by the Imo State Government as an arm of the ministry of Agriculture and Natural Resources, with the responsibility of producing agriculturists of middle level cadre, for the implementation of the State's agricultural policies. The Polytechnic became an autonomous institution with a governing council under edict No. 11 of 1979 (law). It metamorphosed to Michael Okpara College of Agriculture and Technology (MOCATECH) Umuagwo in 2005 following the institution of an administrative panel by the Government of Chief (Dr.) Achike Udenwa in March 30th, 2004 to review the curricular and the structure of the Polytechnic with a view to improving its operational capabilities. The institution was established to provide courses of study, training and research as well as development of

techniques and skills in all branches of agriculture and technology of a standard, leading to the award of National Diploma (ND) and Higher National Diploma (HND). In addition, it provides courses in areas of Pre-ND, Associate certificates and other short courses which are mounted periodically to improve the skills and techniques of agricultural personnel and farmers. It is on record that the institution was the first College of Agriculture in Nigeria to have its programmes accredited by the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) in 1983. (Retrieved September 20, 2014 from, <http://www.nbte.gov.ng/monotechnics.html>, <http://www.imopoly.edu.ng/index.php/about-imo-poly/history>). The institution was finally upgraded to a polytechnic status and known as the Imo State Polytechnic in 2007 following the signing into law of a bill passed by the Imo State House of Assembly by His Excellency, Executive Governor of Imo State, Chief Ikedi Ohakim. The law known as the Imo State Polytechnic law No. 11 of 2007 amended the Edict No. 11 of 1979 that established the institution as a monotechnic (Retrieved September 20, 2014 from, <http://www.imopoly.edu.ng/index.php/about-imo-poly/history>)

Literature Review

In 1943, Dr. Abraham Maslow's article "A Theory of Human Motivation" appeared in *Psychological Review*. This was further expanded upon in his book: "Toward a Psychology of being." The basis of Maslow's theory is that human beings are motivated by unsatisfied needs and that certain lower factors need to be satisfied before higher needs can be satisfied. In his hierarchy of motivation, there are general types of needs; physiological, survival, safety, love and esteem that must be satisfied before a person can act unselfishly. He called these needs "deficiency needs." As long as we are motivated to satisfy these cravings, we are moving towards growth, toward self-actualization. Satisfying needs is healthy, while preventing gratification makes us sick or act evilly, (Maslow, A., 1954).

Another theory is X and Y theories. These theories of human motivation were created and developed by Douglas McGregor at *MIT Sloan School of Management in the 1960s* that have been used in human resource management, organizational behavior, organization communication and organizational development. They describe two contrasting models of workforce motivation. Theory X and theory Y have to do with the perceptions managers hold on their employees, not the way they generally behave. It is attitude not attributes. For McGregor, theory X and Y are not different ends of the same continuum. Rather they are two different continua in themselves. He identified theory X assumptions as individuals that dislike their careers and such people have to be supervised. As for theory Y assumptions, these are individuals like their careers and are willing to take part in responsibilities. Theory Y people do not need supervision and can be expected to turn good productive value in their jobs.

Cole (2000) stated that there are basically two types of motivation theories in psychology. The intrinsic and the extrinsic motivation factors. Intrinsic motivation is the urge that comes from within the individual. Many individuals manifest motivated behavior without the slightest regard to the presence or absence of incentives in their undertakings. The activities themselves are self-motivating to them. For example, a successful business education teacher will not change his job simply on a consideration that more money can be earned if, he goes into business. The answer lies in his job satisfaction. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is the urge that comes as a result of external stimuli i.e. the motivated behavior of the individual can be accounted for by the incentive or reward following his behavior. However, theory based on simple extrinsic rewards is not sufficient in explaining motivated behavior of most human beings. For example, if the activities we engage ourselves in do not give due satisfaction we continuously seek for, no amount of incentives reward can make us stick to these undertakings.

Teaching performance of business education teachers can be adequately motivated through good welfare and/or insurance scheme in order to achieve the desired educational objectives. It is the view of Okeke cited in Ozochi (2009) that administration need to work out an acceptable and functional scheme for the welfare of teachers if business education teachers are to be properly motivated. Therefore, staff administrative motivation brings about systematic arrangement of human and materials resources and programmes that are available for education and carefully wig them within defined guidelines or policies to achieve educational goals.

In-service training for business education teachers is the type of teacher education programme received by people who are already engaged in the teaching profession. That is, an educational programme undertaken by teachers who want to obtain a higher professional knowledge and certificate in teaching profession. It improves the quality of the teachers in the field of teaching. This is because it upgrades the knowledge base of the recipients and qualifies them for promotion in their organizational setting. For instance, business education teachers/workers with TCII certificate studying further to obtain Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) or first degree certificate in Education, Business education lecturers/workers with first degree studying further to obtain Masters in Education (M.Ed) or PhD in Education, (Ejili and Anyanwu, 2006).

Nebeolise (2013) in her empirical studies opined that, one of the major remunerations to teachers in school system is funding and provision of ICT facilities for personal research, teaching and learning process in the classroom. Since the introduction of Information Technology, as an institution of globalization, tertiary institutions in Nigeria have also been providing personal computers for all its staff members to motivate them to work. The computer can be used to link students and facilitators both in formal and informal education set up. The use of computers in the processing of examination results and staff having access to computers aim at minimizing problems associated with manual processing of examination results.

Statement of the Problem

Education in teaching and learning is simply aimed at influencing the learner positively. Effective learning takes place only when the environment is conducive for both the teacher and the learner. Therefore, the man who transfers knowledge and skills to the pupils/students needs to be well motivated as the moral will exert a tremendous influence on the learner. The business education teachers and other staff need to be well paid; they need to be promoted as and when due, their welfare has to be taken care of as it is only when this is done that they will be better prepared to discharge their responsibilities which will in turn affect the performance of the students positively. A teacher who is happy will definitely be ready to impart knowledge to the students while a teacher who is not happy will do otherwise. But today, business education teachers are not adequately motivated to professionally perform creditable in their teaching career. Against this backdrop, it becomes pertinent to ask why business education teachers are not adequately motivated in polytechnics in Imo State. And to what extent does the staff motivation of business education teachers affect their performance in teaching and learning process? These are the problems this study will find out.

Purpose of the Study

The objectives of the study include:

- (i) To determine the effects of job security on teaching performance among business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.

- (ii) To determine the effects of good welfare scheme on teaching performance among business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.
- (iii) To determine the effects of adequate in-service training/scholarships on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.
- (iv) To determine the effects of enhanced salaries and emoluments on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to aid the study:

- (i) What is the effect of job security on teaching performance among business education teachers in polytechnics, Imo State?
- (ii) What is the effect of good welfare scheme on teaching performance among business education teachers in polytechnics, Imo State?
- (iii) What is the effect of adequate in-service training/ scholarships on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics, Imo State?
- (iv) What is the effect of enhanced salaries and emoluments on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics, Imo State?

Research Hypotheses

- (1) There is no significant mean score difference on the perceived effects of motivation in the performance of female and male business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.
- (2) There is no significant mean score difference between motivated teaching staff of business education in federal and state polytechnics in Imo State.

Method

The *survey design* was used for the research. Business education teachers from public-owned polytechnics in Imo State formed the population. The population, with combined staff strength of **195 business education teachers**, comprises of 106 business education teachers from Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri and 87 business education teachers from Imo State Polytechnic Umuagwo Ohaji. These teachers were picked from the departments of the Schools of Business & Management Technology of both polytechnics. The polytechnics were stratified according to ownership and through simple random sampling, 30 business education teachers from 8 departments of the federal polytechnic and 30 business education teachers from 7 departments of the state polytechnic were selected as the sample for the study. In all, **60 business education teaching staff representing 31% of the population** were selected as sample for the study. Instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire known as *Effects of Motivations on Teaching Performance of Business Education Teachers Questionnaire (EMTPBETQ)* was designed and used for data collection. The questionnaire had two parts; part A dealt with bio-data of the respondents and part B focused on the likert item statements. The instrument was validated by experts in education, University of Nigeria, and Enugu State College of education (Technical). 10 teaching staff in one polytechnic in South-south, Nigeria was administered this instrument on two different intervals. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was 0.99 using Cronbach Alpha techniques. 60 copies of the instrument were personally administered by the researcher and all were returned. Thereafter, a criterion mean of 2.50 was established and adopted to serve as basis for acceptance or rejection. A t-test statistic was used to test the research hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results/findings

Research Question 1: What is the effect of job security on teaching performance among business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State?

Table 1: Research Question 1

S/N	Item statements	X	SD	Decision
1.	Job security will increase willingness to teach.	2.83	1.03	Accepted
2.	Job security will increase punctuality and dedication to duty.	2.86	1.11	Accepted
3.	Job security will promote healthy competition among staff.	2.77	1.17	Accepted
4.	Job security will increase willingness to cover the scheme of work.	2.80	1.09	Accepted
5.	Job security will improve classroom management.	2.67	1.05	Accepted

Table 1 has items 1 to 5 with mean scores of 2.83, 2.86, 2.77, 2.80 and 2.67 respectively. This revealed that respondents accepted that willingness to teach and assist the students, punctuality to duty, effective classroom management and healthy competition are the good effects of job security for business education teachers.

Research Question 2: What is the effect of good welfare scheme on teaching performance among business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State?

Table 2: Research Question 2

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
6.	Good welfare scheme will minimize corrupt practices.	2.77	0.99	Accepted
7.	Good welfare scheme will promote good health of teachers.	2.86	1.02	Accepted
8.	Good welfare scheme generates composure during teaching.	2.74	1.01	Accepted
9.	Good welfare scheme increase selfless service to the school management.	2.50	1.14	Accepted
10.	Good welfare scheme helps to promote and protect business education association.	2.84	1.07	Accepted
11.	Good welfare scheme improves willingness to assist the students.	2.92	1.03	Accepted

The items in *table 2* ranged from 6 to 11 with mean scores of 2.77, 2.86, 2.74, 2.50, 2.84 and 2.92, indicating that respondents accepted that good health, selfless services, composure, avoidance of corrupt practices and promotion of business education association are the motivational effects of good welfare scheme on business education teachers.

Research Question 3: What is the effect of adequate in-service training/scholarships on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State?

Table 3: Research Question 3

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
12.	In-service training promotes good communication skills among teaching staff in classrooms	2.83	0.85	Accepted
13.	In-service training creates high ability to conduct research.	2.96	0.83	Accepted
14.	In-service training gives adequate ICT knowledge and skills.	2.97	1.01	Accepted
15.	In-service training creates willingness to the use of ICT in teaching business education.	2.73	0.26	Accepted
16.	In-service training gives willingness to further education.	2.52	0.96	Accepted

The items in *table 3* are between 12 to 16 with mean scores of 2.83, 2.96, 2.97, 2.73 and 2.52 respectively. The respondents accepted that good communication skills, high research abilities, knowledge of ICT and usage and willingness to further education are the motivational effects of in-service training on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.

Research Question 4: What is the effect of enhanced salaries and emoluments on teaching performance of business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State?

Table 4: Research Question 4

S/N	Item Statement	X	SD	Decision
17.	Enhanced salaries and emoluments promote punctual/dedication to teaching duties.	2.92	1.03	Accepted
18.	Enhanced salaries and emoluments check collection of bribes from students.	2.82	0.88	Accepted
19.	Enhanced salaries and emoluments encourage full participation in students' welfare programmes.	2.82	0.79	Accepted
20.	Enhanced salaries and emoluments promote good parent-teacher relationship.	2.77	0.85	Accepted
21.	Enhanced salaries and emoluments encourage conference and seminar participation.	2.90	0.96	Accepted

Table 4 has items 17 to 21 with mean scores of 2.92, 2.82, 2.82, 2.77 and 2.90 respectively. These showed that respondents accepted that regular/punctuality to teaching, non-inclination to bribery, full participation in students' welfare programmes, good parent-teacher relationship, conference and seminar participation are positive motivational effects of enhanced salaries and emoluments on teaching performances among business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant mean score difference on the perceived effects of motivation in the performance of female and male business education teachers in polytechnics in Imo State.

Table 5: T-test Analysis Results of Hypothesis 1

Gender	N	X	SD	Lev..Sig	T-cal	T-cri	Decision
Female	34	0.57	33.43				
DF	58			0.05	0.14	1.98	Not Sign.
Male	26	0.43	25.57				

From Table 5 above, it was revealed that T-calculated value of 0.14 is less than the T-critical of 2.00 with 58 degree of freedom at 0.05 Alpha levels. Null hypothesis is accepted as there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business education teachers on the perceived effects of motivation in teaching performance in public-owned polytechnics in Imo State.

Research Hypothesis 2: There is no significant mean score difference between motivated teaching staff of business education in federal and state polytechnics in Imo State.

Table 6: T-Test Analysis Results of Hypothesis 2

Institution	N	X	SD	Lev..Sig	T-cal	T-cri	Decision
Federal polytechnic	39	0.65	38.35				
DF	58			0.05	0.07	1.98	Not Sign.
State polytechnic	21	0.35	20.65				

From Table 6, it was revealed that T-calculated value of 0.07 is less than the T-critical of 2.00 with 58 degree of freedom at 0.05 Alpha levels. Null hypothesis is accepted as there is no significant difference in the mean rating between federal and state polytechnics on perceived effects of staff motivation on teaching performance of business education teachers in Imo State.

Discussion of the Findings

Table 1 result findings showed that business education teachers are motivated by their willingness to teach as professionals. If their job is given maximum security and are promoted as at when due, it will trigger their willingness to be punctual and dedicated to duty, improve their classroom management and foster healthy competition and willingness to teach. In Table 2, good and adequate welfare scheme for the business education teachers will help to minimize corrupt practices among them in the school, give them good health to

deliver lectures in the classroom, make them to be composed and willing to assist the students in their academic careers or pursuits. Teaching performance of business education teachers can be adequately motivated through good welfare and/or insurance scheme, which are the social process concerned with people, materials and procedures with the intent to achieve the desired educational objectives. It is the view of Okeke cited in Ozochi (2009) that administration needs to work out an acceptable and operable scheme for welfare of teachers if business education teachers are to be properly motivated. Therefore, staff administrative motivation brings about systematic arrangement of human and materials resources and programmes that are available for education and carefully wig them within defined guidelines or policies to achieve educational goals.

Tables 3 and 4 results revealed another finding of the study. In Table 3, results showed that benefits of in-service training to business education teachers are encouraging because, it will increase their motivation in classroom teaching and learning. It will build in them good communication skills when teaching, good application of ICT equipment in classroom teaching and learning, high ability to research and willingness to further their education to higher degree levels. According to Ejili and Anyanwu, (2006), in-service training of business education teachers is the type of teacher education programme received by people who are already engaged in the teaching profession. That is, an educational programme undertaken by teachers who want to obtain a higher professional knowledge and certificate in teaching profession. It improves the quality of the teachers in the field of teaching. This is because it upgrades the knowledge base of the recipients and qualifies them for promotion in their organizational setting. For instance, business education teachers/workers with TC II certificate studying further to obtain Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) or first degree certificate in education, business education lecturers/workers with first degree studying further to obtain Masters in Education (M.Ed) or Ph.D. in education. In Table 4, enhanced salaries and emoluments when properly implemented and regularized with respect to parallel colleagues in the universities, the motivation of business education teachers in polytechnics will be greatly improved. This will ameliorate tendency to collect inducements from the students, foster dedication to duties and curb inferiority complex among serving business education teachers in public-owned polytechnics in Imo State.

The research hypotheses results revealed that mean rating of motivation on teaching performance between male and female business education teachers are not significantly different. *This means that they have the same effects when exposed to the same components of motivation.* The second hypothesis results showed that federal and state polytechnics in Imo State have the same mean rating of teaching performance among business education teachers when motivated. Since the introduction of Information Technology, as a tool of globalization, tertiary institutions in Nigeria have also been providing personal computers for all its staff members to motivate them to work. The computer can be used to link students and facilitators both in formal and informal education set up. The use of computers in processing examination results and staff having access to computers aim at minimizing problems associated with manual processing of examination result, (Nebeolisa, 2013).

Conclusion

Improvement in educational delivery brought about by adequate motivation of business education teachers in our polytechnics might in this case, not mean the ultimate provision of job security, good welfare scheme, enhanced salaries and emoluments and in-service training, but it would most likely bring about a change in teacher behavior which would translate into optimal commitment in teaching, better student performance and general improvement of schools. The society might not be aware that the role of the teacher

in schools calls for sacrifice, perseverance and tolerance; it implies self-control, discipline and respect for self and others (Ofoegbu, 2004). Therefore teachers need appropriate assistance to raise the academic tone of the school, improve the quality of graduates from our polytechnics and reduce absenteeism and lack of commitment to work. Evidently with effective motivation, business education teachers would most likely avoid lackadaisical behaviors that may encourage using the "noble" profession as a stepping-stone for other professions.

Educational Implications

From the findings discussed and conclusion drawn, the following are the educational implications of the study:

If business education teachers are poorly motivated in their teaching duties, students will not properly learn business management and technology skills and will not be able to apply it in the society. This will negatively affect economic transformation of the state and Nigeria in general.

The consequence of non-motivation of business education teachers is that no matter how energetic, enthusiastic and committed a teacher might be, his/her effort and level of performance might not produce the required result in students. Likewise a teacher's action to satisfy motive could be affected by the negative context of the school environment.

Poor motivation in teaching performance of business education teachers will reduce the professionalism of business management and technology teachers in the state, by making it less important as a career. Teachers will no longer be punctual and dedicated to duties and it may lead to truancy in the state education system with serious attempts to jeopardize the government's policies of universal and compulsory education for all.

Lack of motivation may lead to stress which eventually may translate to ineffective classroom management and school improvement.

Motivation is a consistent factor that can be used across professions and other job situations. It would be useful for those who clamor for effectiveness and efficiency at work. This study recognizes the role of teacher motivation in ensuring classroom effectiveness and school improvement. Motivating business education teachers would ensure that there is effective instruction in the classroom and more collaboration in school management. Therefore a teacher needs not only adjustment and regular payment of salary and allowance but consistent training and re-training, good welfare packages and job security towards effective classroom management and school improvement.

Recommendations

Among several other factors, teacher motivation should be included as part of working resources in the education system. Everyone today is concerned with education. Given the importance teachers play in molding students' character, values and morals it is important to see teachers as skilled workers rather than a "cheap" labor to achieve educational objectives. In this era of materialism, display of wealth and corruption in the face of widespread poverty teachers need to be adequately motivated so that they on their part would ensure a viable school system. Government, parents and the society should recognize and appreciate their efforts rather than accuse them for failures that are the obvious results of unfairness and injustice meted out to teachers. From the conclusion drawn, the following are the recommendations which this study is canvassing for:

- (1.) The importance of staff training, retraining and development must be noted and strengthened. Its programmes must be of high quality; relevant to the teaching – learning instructions and built around business education teachers' needs and educational needs.

- (2.) Government should not pay deaf ears to teachers' motivational needs especially in such areas like good salaries or remuneration and promotion.
- (3.) Government must ensure that Business Management and Technology is professionalized in Nigeria, given high recognition and status appropriate to their level of qualifications and responsibilities.
- (4.) Business education teachers should be given room for participatory decision making in the educational system for quality delivery and quality outcomes in the Nigerian educational system.
- (5.) Government provide conducive learning environment and good working conditions as well as provide adequate resources necessary to offer quality education that will guarantee quality assurance in the system. Teachers' welfare should be taken into consideration.
- (6.) Government (federal and state) should provide adequate funds through their annual budgets to strengthen business education teachers' motivational needs.
- (7.) The local communities, NGOs, private sectors and international organizations should as well support business education teachers' motivation by funding seminars and training programmes for them as much possible.
- (8.) The federal government should however re-consider UNESCO's 26% or more to be allocated to education in order to cover unforeseen contingencies and expenses.

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